

Filtering Ideas Using a Tiered Payment System

Abstract

Many people have innovative ideas but lack the opportunity to have them heard by companies. This often results in potentially valuable ideas being overlooked because companies cannot efficiently filter and evaluate every submission. To address this, companies can use a tiered payment system that allows individuals to self-filter their submissions based on their confidence and willingness to invest in their ideas. This system ensures that the most serious and potentially valuable ideas receive the attention they deserve.

Body

Tech companies can implement a four-tiered payment system to filter and prioritize idea submissions. This system allows individuals to choose how much they are willing to invest to have their ideas reviewed, thereby indicating the seriousness and potential value of their submissions.

Tier 1: Free Submission

- **Cost:** Free
- **Review Process:** Ideas submitted for free enter a general pool with no guarantee of review.
- **Reviewer:** Any available employee within the company may review these submissions on a voluntary basis.
- **Notes:** This tier is suitable for individuals who want to submit ideas without any financial investment. However, there is no assurance that their ideas will be reviewed or acted upon.

Tier 2: Small Fee Submission

- **Cost:** \$10 per page or \$0.10 per word
- **Review Process:** Guaranteed review of the idea.
- **Reviewer:** An assigned employee within the company.
- **Notes:** Paying a small fee ensures that the idea will be reviewed by someone within the company, providing a higher chance of consideration.

Tier 3: Medium Fee Submission

- **Cost:** \$30 per page or \$0.30 per word
- **Review Process:** Guaranteed review by a key person in the company.
- **Reviewer:** A key person with decision-making authority relevant to the idea's domain.
- **Notes:** This tier is for individuals who believe their idea has substantial value and want it to be evaluated by someone with significant influence within the company.

Tier 4: Large Fee Submission

- **Cost:** \$100 per page or \$1 per word
- **Review Process:** Guaranteed review directly by the CEO.
- **Reviewer:** The CEO of the company.
- **Notes:** This highest tier is intended for ideas that the submitter is confident are groundbreaking or extremely valuable. It ensures that the idea reaches the top decision-maker in the company.

Example Pricing Table

Nr.	Priority Level	Dollars Page	Dollars Word	Reviewer	Notes
1	Low	0	0	Any employee	No guaranteed review
2	Medium	10	0.10	Assigned employee	Guaranteed review
3	High	30	0.30	Key person in the company	Guaranteed review by a key decision-maker
4	Very High	100	1.00	CEO	Guaranteed review by the CEO

Conclusion

This tiered payment system leverages financial investment as a means to prioritize idea submissions, ensuring that the most serious and potentially valuable ideas receive the attention they deserve. By allowing individuals to self-filter their submissions based on their willingness to pay, companies can more efficiently manage the influx of ideas and focus their resources on the most promising ones.

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